

CERTIFICATE

OF APPRECIATION

TIBBIYOT AKADEMIYASI

JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Yunusova Makhliyo Hikmatilla qizi

**CHARACTERISTICS OF CUTANEOUS MANIFESTATIONS AND
HEMATOLOGICAL PARAMETERS IN CORONAVIRUS INFECTION**

**NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN
TAQDIRLANADI**

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